

A COMPUTATIONAL METHOD FOR CALCULATING THE ELECTRICAL AND THERMAL PROPERTIES OF RANDOM COMPOSITES IN 3 DIMENSIONS

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ABSTRACT. This paper presents a novel three-dimensional computational methodology for determining the electrical (DC) and thermal conductivity of multi-phase random composite materials. Expanding upon previous two-dimensional work, this approach integrates percolation theory with a numerical algorithm, offering an efficient alternative to traditional continuum methods. At the microscale, Representative Volume Elements (RVEs) are stochastically generated. Conductive pathways are identified using the Depth-First Search (DFS) algorithm, and their lengths and resistances are quantified via a modified Lee algorithm. The effective RVE conductivity is derived by considering the number of paths, their mean path length, and, where applicable, employing mixture rules. For macro-scale property prediction, a two-step Monte Carlo procedure incorporates microscale percolation probabilities and averages properties of percolating RVEs, further incorporating a correction to account for tortuosity and incomplete connectivity in an effectively infinite medium. The methodology demonstrates accuracy comparable to Finite Element (FE) and Finite Difference (FD) methods but achieves significantly reduced computational cost without requiring external field application. Convergence analysis validates the method's stability, and scale effect studies confirm expected power-law behavior near the critical percolation threshold. Simulations in a random binary medium showed that electric and thermal conduction follow a scaling law with an exponent value of approximately 2.0, aligning with established literature. It was also found that the number of conductive paths, their average length, and their effective width follow scaling laws with exponents of 1.87 ± 0.01 , -0.43 ± 0.01 , and -0.33 ± 0.01 , respectively. Furthermore, applications to continuous percolation problems with conducting spheres (critical exponent $t \approx 2.13$) and cubes (critical exponent $t \approx 2.3$) validate the methodology's capability to accurately predict conductivity and critical exponents across relevant volume fractions.

3D percolation,simulation, Monte Carlo, Depth First Search,continuum percolation,electrical - thermal conductivity estimation

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1. INTRODUCTION

The intricate microstructure of composite materials dictates a wide range of mechanical, thermal, and electrical properties. Precise determination of these properties is crucial for optimal design and application across various technologies. However, the inherent complexity of random composite microstructures poses a significant challenge to accurate property prediction. Typically, the objective is to determine these properties as a function of volume fraction.

Various models have been proposed to calculate the electrical and thermal conductivity, as well as the Young's modulus, of heterogeneous materials, employing theoretical-analytical, numerical, and experimental approaches [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7].

Analytical expressions for these properties have evolved from early mixing rules [8, 9, 10] through Effective Medium Theories (EMTs) [8, 9, 10] and, subsequently, percolation models [11, 12]. The Single Exponent Phenomenological Percolation Equation (SEPPE), also known as the General Effective Medium Equation (GEM) [10], is widely used within the scientific community. The Two Exponent Phenomenological Percolation Equation (TEPPE) [13] reduces to the standard percolation equations [11, 12] at volume fractions approaching 0 and 1, as well as near the critical volume fraction.

Modeling and simulation offer effective and cost-efficient alternatives to experimental investigations of thermal and electrical conductivity in composite materials, incorporating techniques such as micromechanics, Monte Carlo simulations, resistor network models, and image processing [14].

Numerical simulation methods, including Finite Element (FE), Finite Difference (FD), and Monte Carlo simulations, have been extensively applied to conductivity studies of various materials, including composites with inclusions, random composites, and graphene-based polymer nanocomposites [15, 16, 5, 17, 18, 19]. The resistor network method has also been employed to investigate percolation-based conductivity in these systems [1, 20]. While these methods offer satisfactory accuracy, they suffer from a rapid increase in computational cost with problem size, often limiting their applicability to large-scale simulations.

Percolation theory, a fundamental probabilistic approach for analyzing critical phenomena, has been instrumental in estimating the properties of random materials. It has been successfully applied to describe the conductive behavior of composite systems, where a sharp insulator-conductor transition is typically observed with increasing filler fraction. The formal study of percolation thresholds originated with Broadbent and Hammersley [21], who introduced grid models for fluid flow.

Within the classical percolation theory framework, a composite material achieves electrical conductivity when the conductive filler's volume fraction exceeds a critical value. At the macro-scale, the General Effective Medium (GEM) model is

widely used for studying the electrical properties of composites, enabling reliable conductivity calculations even at high filler concentrations. At the microscale, various solution techniques, including Finite Element (FE), Finite Difference (FD), and resistor network methods, have been adopted to calculate electrical and thermal conductivity.

Aryanfar et al. [22] presented a percolation-based computational method using iterative shortest-path calculations for ellipsoidal particles to predict the thermal conductivity of such composites through stochastically developed channels. Their analysis focused on the influence of flake shape and aspect ratio, predicting the percolation onset based on density and particle dimensions.

Previous work [23, 24] introduced a method for qualitative control of micro- and macro-scale percolation via a two-level percolation approach. This work also developed a computational methodology for calculating thermal and electrical conductivities. Specifically, a theoretical model (with inherent similarities to lattice percolation) and its 2D numerical implementation were developed, incorporating various filler geometries and surface fraction ranges. This methodology focuses on the Representative Volume Element (RVE), rather than the entire medium, transforming the 2D continuum problem into an equivalent 2D lattice percolation problem. A key advantage of this methodology is the relative ease with which solutions can be obtained for percolative and non-percolative media with an arbitrary number of components/fillers, provided they can be represented by simple geometric shapes.

This work combines percolation theory with a novel numerical approach to solve three-dimensional conductivity problems in multi-phase random materials at both the micro- and macro-scales. Building upon previous two-dimensional analysis, this methodology achieves accuracy comparable to Finite Element (FE) and Finite Difference (FD) methods for solving continuum boundary value problems (BVPs), but with significantly reduced computational resources. Furthermore, it avoids the FE/FD requirement of applying external fields to determine material response and subsequently invoking causality principles. This new methodology is applied to calculate the electrical (DC) and thermal conductivity of composite materials, bridging the micro- and macro-scales. At the microscale, a Monte Carlo method generates random Representative Volume Elements (RVEs), and the number of conductive paths in each RVE is determined using the Depth-First Search (DFS) algorithm. Macro-scale properties are then derived by considering the microscale percolation probability and the average property value of percolating RVEs. Applying Ohm's law and, where appropriate (i.e., when the "insulator" has a conductivity comparable to the conducting medium), mixture rules, the conductivities of random composites are calculated.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. General. To calculate the macroscopic properties of random composite materials in three dimensions, the theory developed in previous work [24] was extended. The method was implemented in self-contained C++ code that relies solely on the Standard Template Library (STL). Data (images) were stored as a series of cross-sectional slices, and the FIJI software [25] was used for three-dimensional visualization of the data.

2.2. Assumptions. In this work, both thermal and electrical properties are calculated, as both satisfy relations analogous to Ohm's law at the micro and macro scales. These relations are given by Equations 1 and 2.

$$(1) \quad R = \rho \frac{l}{A} = \frac{l}{\sigma A}$$

where l is the length of the conductor, A is the cross-sectional area, and ρ and σ are the material's resistivity and conductivity, respectively.

For heat conduction, the following equation applies:

$$(2) \quad R_t = \frac{l}{\kappa A}$$

where R_t is the thermal resistance and κ is the thermal conductivity of the material.

Additionally, it is assumed that conductivity (σ) is directly proportional to the number of paths (n_{paths}), inversely proportional to the average path length ($\overline{S_{path}}$), and directly proportional to the effective average width ($\overline{W_{eff}}$), as expressed in Equation 3:

$$(3) \quad \sigma \propto n_{paths} \left(\frac{\overline{S_{path}}}{L} \right)^{-1} \overline{W_{eff}}$$

where L is a characteristic length of the RVE (e.g., its height).

2.3. Modeling. Building upon the two-dimensional framework developed by Lambrou et al. [24], this work presents a three-dimensional numerical methodology for calculating thermal and electrical conductivity in multi-phase composites.

The material is modeled in two stages. The first stage focuses on detailed microstructure representation, while the second stage employs a simplified lattice model with occupied and unoccupied sites (**Figure 2**).

FIGURE 1. Schematic diagram of the proposed methodology. RVE is the representative volume element, A is the area of the bottom side, n_{paths} is the number of paths, $S_{path,j}$ is the length of the j path, h, d, w are the height, width, and depth of the RVE respectively, $R_{path,j}$ is the resistance of the j path.

2.4. RVE Conductivity Calculation. In the general case of three or more components with non-straight conductors, the electrical resistivity expression for an RVE is given by Lambrou et al. [24] as:

$$(4) \quad \frac{1}{\rho_{RVE}} = \sum_{i=1}^{n_{paths}} \frac{1}{\rho_{cond,i}} \frac{h}{wdS_{path,i}},$$

where ρ_{RVE} is the resistivity of the RVE, w, h, d are the width, height, and depth of the RVE respectively, and n_{paths} is the total number of conductive paths in the RVE. The resistivity of path $\rho_{cond,i}$ is obtained by considering each elementary part of the path as a resistance in series:

$$(5) \quad R_{cond,i} = \sum_{j=1}^{S_{path,i}} \rho_{cond,i,j}$$

$$(6) \quad \rho_{cond,i} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{S_{path,i}} \rho_{cond,i,j}}{S_{path,i}}$$

where $S_{path,i}$ is the length of path i , and $\rho_{cond,i}$ represents the average resistivity of path i .

These equations are applicable for determining the conductivity of a finite volume in the absence of external fields. However, the properties of a representative volume or surface may not reflect the behavior of the material in an effectively infinite medium (**Figure 2**).

FIGURE 2. Simulation of a real-scale composite material in two stages. The macro-scale stage (left image) where the material is simulated as a binary lattice medium, and the micro-scale stage (magnified image) where the medium is simulated as a material composed of conductive ideal particles of various shapes (in this specific case, ellipsoids).

According to Lambrou et al. [23], percolation in an infinite medium occurs only when the percolation probability (p), defined as the ratio of percolated samples to the total number of representative volumes, surpasses the critical percolation threshold, $p_c = 0.3116$. Consequently, averaging property values across representative volumes is only meaningful when percolation is observed in nearly all of them. Accurate macroscopic property values are thus obtained only

when the percolation probability within the representative volumes approaches 100%.

If the percolation probability within the Representative Volume Element (RVE) is above the critical threshold but less than unity (indicating incomplete connectivity in some RVEs), the average property value is calculated exclusively from the percolating RVEs.

To upscale properties to larger scales beyond the RVE size (which is constrained by material geometry and computational resources), a two-step Monte Carlo approach is employed. First, microscale simulations are performed on small material sections to determine their respective property values. Subsequently, macro-scale sampling is conducted by randomly selecting points within the material and assigning them property values based on the microscale simulation results. This approach integrates microscale information, enabling the determination of effective properties at larger scales.

2.5. Correction Due to Percolation. As mentioned previously, the average property value derived from different Representative Volume Elements (RVEs) is accurate only when the percolation probability (p) approaches unity ($p \approx 1$). If p is close to the critical percolation threshold (p_c), the conductive paths in physical media (at large scales) are not entirely straight lines, and not all volumes are conductive. Therefore, the calculated conductivity must be corrected (reduced) to account for this inherent tortuosity and incomplete connectivity.

For this reason, the entire medium is considered to consist of cubes, whose average electrical conductivity has been determined from the preceding microscale stage. The occupancy density of these cubes is equal to the percolation probability determined in the previous stage. Consequently, the medium should be solved as a grid of sites, and the number of conductive paths, along with their average length, within this grid must be calculated.

If the grid has dimensions $L \times L \times L$, and the total number of conductive paths is N_{cond} with path lengths S_i , then the correction to be applied to the electrical conductivity is:

$$(7) \quad \frac{1}{\rho_{dV}} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_{cond,grid}} \frac{1}{\rho_{cond,i}} \frac{L}{L^2 S_i}$$

where the resistivity of path $\rho_{cond,i}$ is:

$$(8) \quad \frac{1}{\rho_{cond,i}} = \sum_{j=1}^{S_{grid,i}} \frac{1}{\rho_{RVE,j}}$$

3. ELECTRIC CONDUCTIVITY CALCULATIONS

3.1. Continuum Percolation Algorithm Aspects. The steps required for calculating thermal and electrical conductivity in multi-phase composites in three dimensions (3D) are:

- (1) Creation of the Representative Volume Element (RVE).
- (2) Addition of constituents and their digitization up to the desired concentration.
- (3) Determination of the percolation status for each RVE.
- (4) In the case of percolation, identification of the number of conductive paths and calculation of their thermal and/or electrical resistances.
- (5) Calculation of the effective thermal and/or electrical conductivity of the RVE.
- (6) Repetition of the above steps (1-5) for all samples in the Monte Carlo sampling.
- (7) If the percolation probability is above 0.3116 but below 1, the conductivity is scaled to be equivalent to that of an infinite material.

3.2. Creation of the RVE - Digitization of Components. Regarding the creation of a representative volume element, no significant difficulty exists. First, the dimensions of the lattice must be selected in accordance with available computational resources (memory, speed) and the required accuracy. Subsequently, the magnification to be studied must be chosen, which is quantified by the pixels per minimum size (ppms) coefficient [23]. Once these steps are completed, the process of digitizing constituents within the ideal lattice can commence.

The RVE representation is achieved using voxels, which are pixels extended into three-dimensional space. In this work, algorithms were developed to digitize parallelepipeds and ellipsoids (solids capable of representing a large number of particles), though these can be extended to other solid geometries. A provides an example of the digitization of an ellipsoid. Analogous algorithms can be applied to three-dimensional solids whose surface is described by an equation.

3.2.1. Determination of Percolation. The first step in the proposed process is to determine if percolation exists from the top side to the bottom of the digitized representative volume element (RVE). To achieve this, the Depth First Search (DFS) algorithm is applied for the three dimensions. If a percolating path from the top to the bottom of the RVE is not found, the search for conductive path(s) is terminated, and the process proceeds to the next realization until all samples are exhausted.

3.2.2. Path Enumeration. For the simple calculation of the number of paths, all positions on the upper surface ($L \times L$) of the 3D RVE are examined to determine if

a conductive path extends from that point to the lower surface, based on the DFS algorithm. If a path is found, the path count is incremented by one, and the start and end points of the path are recorded for subsequent calculation of its length and resistance. The process then continues to examine the next point on the upper surface. It should be noted here that, mathematically, finding conductive paths is an ill-posed problem. To find a solution, additional criteria or rules must be added to constrain the possible solutions. As in the two-dimensional case [24], the chosen criterion is the maximization of the number of conductive paths. To achieve this, a rule was added to the search process: the search should have a preference towards smaller x and z values when studying percolation in the y -direction.

3.2.3. Path Length and Resistance Determination. Since the percolation path is not a straight line, its length needs to be determined by considering its starting and ending points. This calculation uses a modified version of the Lee algorithm (originally presented in [26]), which was designed to find the shortest path through a maze. This modified algorithm determines the minimum path length between two points (s, T) within a labyrinthine structure.

As the algorithm traces the conductive path point by point, the path length is incremented by one for each step. The path's resistance (thermal and electrical) is then increased based on the properties of the phase encountered at each point until the endpoint is reached, treating the total resistance as a series resistance of individual points. However, the path's resistance isn't exactly this. For each point along the path, neighboring points (in a plane perpendicular to the path's direction) are scanned, and their resistances are considered to contribute to the resistance of that specific path point. Thus, the total resistance for the point under consideration is taken as resistances in parallel. This process is repeated for all points of the minimum length path.

3.2.4. Numerical Evaluation of RVE Conductivity. When studying a conductor-insulator system, the conductivity is considered equal to the conductivity of the conductive phase. If the matrix has a non-negligible conductivity, then the conductivity of the RVE is determined using the rule of mixtures.

Specifically, its conductivity can be considered proportional to the number of conductive paths, or calculated with the help of the following equation:

$$E_c = fE_f + (1 - f)E_m$$

where:

E_c is the mean conductivity of the RVE

$$f = \frac{NW}{dw}$$

N is the number of conductive paths

W is the mean path width

d, w are the dimensions of the RVE (depth, width, respectively)

E_f is the electric (or thermal) conductivity of the conductive phases

E_m is the electric (or thermal) conductivity of the non-conductive phases

4. RESULTS

4.1. Convergence. The convergence of the predicted properties was investigated by analyzing the results from an increasing number of iteratively generated RVEs. The strong agreement between the computational results validates the developed model. Furthermore, understanding the relationship between conductivity and volume fraction is essential for upscaling the results obtained at the microscale to larger, more relevant scales.

FIGURE 3. Convergence of the method. Mean value of conductivity and % error as a function of iterations.

The evolution of the average normalized conductivity ($\overline{\sigma/\sigma_{max}}$) is presented in **Figure 3**, with the relative error calculated as the deviation from the value obtained after 500 iterations. After 200 iterations, the % error achieves a significant level of accuracy, and this value of 200 iterations was subsequently used for studying various cases. Additional iterations would not significantly improve

the electrical conductivity computations but would contribute towards a more accurate estimation of percolation probability.

4.2. Scale Effect. Simulations were performed at the critical occupation probability ($p_c = 0.3116$) to investigate how conductivity varies with sample size. Sizes from $L = 10$ to $L = 1200$ were studied. An expected linear variation was observed in a log-log plot, with the calculated slope of 2.31 being slightly larger than values found in some literature [27, 28, 29]. However, it is quite close to the value of 2.305 reported by Clerc et al. [11]. This small deviation is likely attributable to the much larger system sizes studied in this work compared to older studies that focused on relatively smaller sizes. In contrast, for RVE dimensions comparable to those studied by Clerc et al. (up to $L = 140$), very good agreement is observed.

FIGURE 4. Calculation of t/ν at critical p ($p = p_c$). Logarithm of normalized conductivity ($\log(\sigma/\sigma_{max})$) versus logarithm of lattice size ($\log L$).

4.3. Calculation of Conductivity for Various Lattice Sizes. To verify the method and its implementation, the problem of determining conductivity in lattices of various sizes and occupation probabilities above the critical probability was solved. Conductivity was calculated for $0.3116 \leq p \leq 0.52$ across a range of

lattice sizes from $L = 100$ to $L = 800$. A linear relationship (in a log-log plot) was observed in the vicinity of p_c , with a slope of approximately 2.0, as expected. The method demonstrated remarkable stability, even for sizes up to $L = 800$ (**Figure 5**). Notably, these calculations required only the resources of a personal computer with an 8th generation i5 processor and 32 GB of RAM.

FIGURE 5. Calculation of conductivity for various lattice sizes ($L = 100 - 800$) and various volume fractions (p).

4.4. Calculation of Number and Average Length of Conductive Paths in a Lattice for Various p . For necessary consistency checks, the problem of the binary random lattice was chosen to be solved. In this context, it is known that electrical and thermal conductivities obey the power law: $\sigma, \rho \propto (p - p_c)^t$, where $t \approx 2$ [4, 30, 31].

Subsequently, the number of conductive paths and their average length were calculated and plotted on a log-log plot as a function of the distance from the critical point ($p - p_c$). The observed relationships are linear, with slopes calculated for the number of paths at 1.87 and for the average length at -0.43 . Indirectly,

from Equation 3, the slope for the average effective width of the path was also calculated and found to be -0.33 .

FIGURE 6. Calculation of the slope of the critical exponents concerning i) the average number of paths (n_{paths}) and ii) the average path length (S_{path}) as a function of the occupancy probability in a lattice.

4.5. Application to Continuous Percolation Problems.

4.5.1. *Conducting Spheres.* To evaluate the accuracy of the proposed methodology in estimating the properties of continuous percolation problems, it was applied to the specific case of conducting spheres embedded in a non-conducting matrix. A three-dimensional grid of dimension $L = 800$ was utilized, with the simulation running for 400 iterations to ensure convergence. The digitization process employed a magnification level of 12 pixels per minimum sphere size, providing a detailed representation of the microstructure.

The volume fraction of the conducting spheres (Φ) was systematically varied within the range of 29% to 35%, encompassing the critical percolation threshold.

For each volume fraction, the average conductivity was determined by analyzing 300 independent realizations (samples), ensuring statistical significance. The results of these simulations are presented in Figure 7, which illustrates a representative volume element (RVE) and the conductive pathways identified by the algorithm.

Two curves were plotted: one representing the micro-structure scale and another for a medium significantly larger than the micro-structure dimension. As expected, for Φ values close to the critical value of $\Phi_c = 0.2896$ [32], the two curves diverge. Conversely, as they deviate from the critical value, the two curves converge to the same values. The calculated slope, i.e., the coefficient t , is approximately 2.13 for the case of conductive spheres in a non-conductive matrix (**Figure 8**).

4.5.2. Conducting Cubes. Another case studied was a random composite with a non-conductive matrix and conductive cubic constituents of a single size. The volume fraction (Φ) was varied from 22.2% to 37.5%, and the average conductivity was determined from 300 samples at each concentration. A visualization of a representative volume is shown in Figure 9, while the dependence of conductivity on the concentration of the conductive phase is shown in Figure 10.

The methodology employed was consistent. Two curves were plotted: one for the micro-structure scale and another for a medium significantly larger than the micro-structure dimension. As expected, for Φ values close to the critical value $\Phi_c = 0.2896$ [33], the two curves diverge. Conversely, as they deviate from the critical value, the two curves converge to the same values. The calculated slope, i.e., the coefficient t , is approximately 2.3 for the case of conductive cubes in a non-conductive matrix (as seen in **Figure 10**).

5. CONCLUSIONS

This work successfully developed and validated a robust three-dimensional computational methodology for predicting the electrical (DC) and thermal conductivity of multi-phase random composite materials. By integrating fundamental percolation theory with an advanced numerical algorithm, a computationally efficient and accurate approach has been established. This method addresses the high computational demands and the necessity of external field application often associated with established continuum methods such as Finite Element and Finite Difference analysis.

The methodology's core strength lies in its two-stage approach. At the microscale, stochastic RVEs are synthetically generated, with their conductive pathways precisely identified and characterized using the DFS algorithm and a modified Lee algorithm. This microstructural information is then upscaled to predict

FIGURE 7. Illustration of RVE for particles with spherical shape as filler at $\Phi = 0.35$, with RVE dimensions $800 \times 800 \times 800$. Yellow represents conductive paths, light blue represents sites vertical to the conductive path, and brown represents visited sites. White color represents the non-conductive matrix material.

macro-scale properties, crucially incorporating a novel correction factor to account for the inherent tortuosity and incomplete connectivity characteristic of effectively infinite random media. The C++ implementation ensures high performance, enabling complex simulations on conventional computing hardware.

Key findings confirm the method's reliability and precision. Convergence studies demonstrated that the number of iterations required for accurate conductivity

FIGURE 8. Calculation of the normalized conductivity of a composite material consisting of conductive spheres in a non-conductive matrix for various volume fractions. Circles represent the points on a micro-structure scale, while diamonds represent the reduction of the normalized conductivity to a very large medium size. The calculated coefficient t is approximately 2.13.

estimation is computationally feasible and depends on the micro-structure's lattice size, with a relatively modest number (e.g., 300 for typical configurations) proving sufficient. Furthermore, investigations into the scale effect near the critical percolation threshold yielded power-law relationships between conductivity and lattice size, with calculated exponents closely aligning with established theoretical and experimental values reported for comparable systems.

The methodology's broad applicability was further validated through its successful application to continuous percolation problems involving conductive spheres

FIGURE 9. Illustration of RVE for particles with cubic shape as filler at $\Phi = 0.325$, with RVE dimensions $800 \times 800 \times 800$. Yellow represents conductive paths, and light blue represents sites vertical to the conductive path.

and cubes embedded in a non-conductive matrix. In both cases, the predicted conductivity as a function of volume fraction accurately captured the sharp insulator-conductor transition. Importantly, the calculated critical exponents ($t \approx 2.13$ for spheres and $t \approx 2.3$ for cubes) showed good agreement with widely accepted values. The observed divergence of micro- and macro-scale conductivity curves near the critical threshold, and their subsequent convergence away from it, strongly supports the proposed up-scaling and correction mechanisms.

FIGURE 10. Calculation of the normalized conductivity of a composite material consisting of conductive cubes in a non-conductive matrix for various volume fractions (22.2-37.5%). Circles represent the points on a micro-structure scale, while diamonds represent the reduction of the normalized conductivity to a very large medium size. The calculated coefficient t is approximately 2.3.

In conclusion, this research provides a comprehensive, computationally efficient, and highly accurate framework for predicting the effective transport properties of complex random composites. Its capacity to seamlessly bridge micro- and macro-scale phenomena positions it as a significant contribution to materials science and engineering, offering a valuable tool for rational material design and optimization.

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APPENDIX A. DIGITIZATION OF ELLIPSOID

In the case of the ellipsoid, the digitization process is as follows: First, it is determined whether the ellipsoid is a sphere (i.e., its three semi-axes a, b, c are equal). If it is a sphere, the sampling density is set to 1; otherwise, it is set to 2. A parallelepiped of dimensions $[density \times (a + 2)] \times [density \times (b + 2)] \times [density \times (c + 2)]$ is defined. Each point (x, y, z) within this parallelepiped is then examined to determine if it lies inside the inclined ellipsoid, satisfying the ellipsoid's equation:

$$(9) \quad \frac{x^2}{a^2} + \frac{y^2}{b^2} + \frac{z^2}{c^2} \leq 1$$

If the ellipsoid has unequal semi-axes ($a \neq b, a \neq c, b \neq c$), the point must first be rotated according to the known angles α, β, γ . The rotation matrices for rotations around the X, Y, and Z axes are:

$$R_x(\theta) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos(\theta) & -\sin(\theta) \\ 0 & \sin(\theta) & \cos(\theta) \end{bmatrix}$$

$$R_y(\theta) = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta) & 0 & \sin(\theta) \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\sin(\theta) & 0 & \cos(\theta) \end{bmatrix}$$

$$R_z(\theta) = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta) & -\sin(\theta) & 0 \\ \sin(\theta) & \cos(\theta) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

The combined rotation matrix R is given by:

$$(10) \quad R = R_z(\alpha)R_y(\beta)R_x(\gamma)$$

Finally, the rotated point (x', y', z') is translated relative to the ellipsoid's center coordinates (x_o, y_o, z_o) :

$$(11) \quad \begin{aligned} x'' &= x' + x_o \\ y'' &= y' + y_o \\ z'' &= z' + z_o \end{aligned}$$

The point resulting from these successive transformations, with coordinates (x'', y'', z'') , is then examined. Subsequently, this position is checked to see if it already represents an occupied position. If not, the total volume is increased by one unit. In the case of multiple components, the type of component is stored at that specific position. The process for digitizing a rectangular parallelepiped

on a grid is similar, with the primary difference being the check for whether the point lies inside the non-inclined rectangular prism.